

THE IMPORTANCE OF DIGITAL STORYTELLING IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract: This article discusses the use of digital storytelling in the practice of teaching foreign languages. Digital Storytelling uses animation, photo, audio and video materials that exist only on electronic media which combines visual, imaginary musical and verbal components and satisfying the cognitive needs of students with different learning styles. And in this work, there are given examples of innovative resources that promote the development of communication skills, a digital online tool is considered to effectively organize the process of teaching foreign languages.

Key words: digital storytelling, communication technologies, digital resources, pedagogical methods, innovative techniques, educational activities.

Modern technological advances in education and language teaching in particular have resulted in a vast amount of resources, knowledge and information readily accessible to language learners. However, one of the most challenging aspects of adopting this technology for teachers, practitioners, and researchers is equipping learners with the skills necessary to effectively use modern technology in their learning processes. Knowledge is not only passed on from teachers to learners. In practice, however, it is constructed by individual students or groups through active interaction with their social, physical and technological environments.

At the present stage, the development of information and communication technologies, the traditional story is replaced by a digital analogue. It is known abroad as Digital Storytelling which with the development of Internet technologies and the emergence of a large number of educational resources has become increasingly used by teachers of foreign languages, for solving various pedagogical problems on all levels of education: from elementary school to universities.

Education is inevitably moving towards digitalization. Before modern teacher of a foreign language raises the question of a competent choice and the use of digital resources to form a foreign language communicative competence. According to digital requirements economics in educational organizations there is a need to create conditions for improving the digital literacy of students, respectively, and

modernization of the structure of the educational process, introducing of digital tools in educational activities.

In its simplest form, digital storytelling refers to the practice of using computer-based tools to tell stories or present ideas. Digital stories have also been defined as multimedia presentations that combine a variety of digital elements within a narrative structure. As opposed to traditional storytelling that uses materials on physical media such as paper, tapes or discs, and film, a digital story uses material that exists on electronic files. As such, digital stories may include not only text, images, video, and audio, but also interactive elements like maps and social media.

Educators in the 21st century believe that technology can be an effective tool in educating the new generation, making learning goals easier to achieve. Digital storytelling has proved its potential as a powerful teaching and learning tool for engaging both teachers and students. Moreover, teachers and instructors can also use digital stories to their advantage. Teachers can create digital storytelling to generate interest and engagement for students of the “YouTube generation”. Digital stories can appeal to diverse learning styles, allowing instructors to present abstract or conceptual information in a more understandable way.

Digital are further stated that multimedia tools such as digital storytelling provides students with opportunities to participate and interact in the classroom, while gaining new skills such as synthesis, analysis, and evaluation. Dillon (2014) also lists down a number of benefits associated with using digital storytelling as an educational tool:

- **Digital storytelling creates** space for meaningful listening. Digital stories provide students with the opportunity to digest information in a meaningful way. This is particularly important in an age where people are bombarded with stories and information. Digital stories allow teachers to genuinely engage students in the story’s message.
- **Digital storytelling persuades** the brain and the heart. Digital stories can teach students the value of emotional rhetoric, allowing them to explore new ways of acting or thinking differently. These stories can elicit emotional responses in students and encourage them to pursue topics that they’re passionate about.
- **The method allows** students to showcase their learning to their peers. Students benefit not only from receiving information through digital stories but also from making digital stories that feature their experiences and learnings. The many aspects of creating a digital story improve students’ technical skills and hone research and writing skills as well.

The rationale for this project is to explore the pedagogical benefits of digital storytelling. Therefore, the overall research question is: How can digital storytelling

enhance the student engagement and provide better educational outcomes for learners? This question can be divided into the following sub-questions:

1. How can digital storytelling be used to enhance student engagement?
2. How can digital storytelling be used to improve educational outcomes?
3. What are teacher perceptions about student learning through digital storytelling?

Scientific resources describe storytelling as a way of influencing people through stories, which is used for various purposes in many professional fields. As well as, digital storytelling is becoming one of the most effective innovative pedagogical techniques that implement the formation of a foreign language communicative competence using digital technology in the process of teaching foreign languages.

At the initial stage of training, when the development of oral speech skills is dominant in connection with the advance speech to speech, younger students often experience stress if necessary to speak in front of a relatively large or, less often unfamiliar audience. Moreover, there is a whole a movement of like-minded people among those who teaches, and among those who study a foreign language, who use in their practice digital storytelling. Therefore, there are many methods to help for eager learners and a huge number of educational websites where you can get acquainted with the technology of digital storytelling.

One of the most famous sites describing the basics of applying this technologies in education, digitalstorytelling.coe.uh.edu - offers the following algorithm for creating a digital story.

Step 1. Decide on a story idea.

Step 2. Find the information you need.

Step 3: Plan your scenario

Step 4: Make a plan.

Step 5. Select the right materials (photo, audio, video).

Step 6. Combine your all story.

Step 7. Share the story in speech with the whole group.

Step 8. Get feedback and think what was particularly successful, and what needs to be improved.

This universal technique, which underlies the game, opens up a unique opportunity for the development of children's communicative competence, facilitates memorizing the plot, and is effective in the process of reasoning. Thus, using this interactive method of organizing children's activities, we will be able to hear every child in the group and help him develop a competent coherent speech.

On the whole, it should be noted that digital storytelling technology justifies the time spent on teaching students how to use digital tools, stimulates intrinsic motivation to learn, improves results in language acquisition. Its use makes the process of mastering the language more vivid and successful. Furthermore, the digital storytelling technique does not require any expenses and can be used anywhere and anytime, since it requires a minimum of additional equipment.

Finally, be aware that storytelling is highly personal and can trigger emotions. This is not necessarily a bad thing but it is important to be prepared. Taking these limitations into account, digital storytelling is a fascinating activity, and one that will enrich your classroom.

In conclusion, I would like to emphasize that all methods and exercises create favorable conditions for imitating a foreign language environment, contribute to the intensive use of vocabulary, develop a sense of language, and the ability to work with text. In this case, the teacher provides children with maximum independence in creativity, does not give direct instructions, helps to act independently, and as a result of careful observation and evaluation, determines their strengths and weaknesses. Students must act independently in the lesson during the games, always show their initiative, whatever it may be.

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